

USE OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN SECONDARY EDUCATION ITS ROLE IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LESSONS

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Annotation: *This article is about using ICT in a classroom which is as a tool for language learning has a lot more benefit. It gives stimulus to undertake the tasks that the students may otherwise avoid. In an ICT enabled language learning class, the students would conduct the activities on the computer software platform and they will not have any sorts of hesitations or inhibitions. It would make repetitive tasks more interesting and would have content which could be in multimedia formats.*

Key words: *ICT, role, tool, multimedia, computer, use, learning, motivation.*

The use of information and communication technologies in teaching English plays a very important role. They help to implement a person-centered approach to learning, provide individualization and differentiation of learning, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning, and aptitudes. At English lessons, you can use a computer to solve a number of didactic tasks: to form reading skills and skills, to improve the writing skills of students; to replenish the vocabulary of students; to form a stable motivation for students to learn English. The world of the latest information technologies is taking an increasing place in our lives. Using them in the classroom increases the motivation and cognitive activity of students of all ages, expands their horizons. Modern pedagogical technologies such as collaborative learning, project methodology, the use of new information and communication technologies Internet resources help to implement a person-oriented approach to learning, provide individualization and differentiation of learning based on the abilities of children, their level of learning, and aptitudes. The modern computer is an effective tool for optimizing the conditions of intellectual labor in General, in any of its manifestations. Forms of working with computer training programs in foreign language lessons include: learning vocabulary; practice pronunciation; teaching Dialogic and monological speech; learning to write; working out grammatical phenomena. At English lessons, you can use a computer to solve a number of didactic tasks: to form reading skills and skills, to improve the writing skills of students; to replenish the vocabulary of students; to form a stable motivation for students to learn

English. The world of the latest information technologies is taking an increasing place in our lives. Using them in the classroom and/or increases the motivation and cognitive activity of students of all ages, expands their horizons. Information and communication technologies contribute to the strengthening of educational motivation for learning and improving students' knowledge. ICTs are aimed at intensifying the learning process, improving the forms and methods of organizing the educational process. The use of computers in English lessons significantly increases the intensity of the educational process. In computer-based learning, a much larger amount of material is learned than was done at the same time in traditional learning. In addition, the material is absorbed more strongly when using a computer. Another advantage of the computer is the ability to accumulate statistical information during the educational process. Analyzing statistical data (number of errors, correct / incorrect responses, requests for help, time spent on individual tasks.), the teacher judges the degree and quality of students' knowledge formation. When teaching phonetics, you can use presentations with audio and video materials, dictionary articles voiced by native speakers. It is also very important to take into account age characteristics and language proficiency. When practicing sounds, you can use training programs that monitor the pronunciation of words, and the child will not be able to go to a new stage without pronouncing the previous lexical units correctly. Reading is an integral part of language learning. Hypertexts are very helpful at this stage. Hypertext is an opportunity not only to read the text, but also to study in more detail the phenomena that occur in the text. At the initial stage, you can use various simulators with exercises such as "insert the missing letter, find the same letter, divide the words according to the rules of reading, etc." Using ICT in lessons when working out grammatical forms, children learn the information received in a visual form much faster than just using diagrams and tables. When a child sees a situation, he lives it and finds himself in it. The use of multimedia presentations makes it possible to control the attention of students due to animation effects; increase the motivation of teaching; systematization of the studied material; formation of computer multimedia competence, both for the teacher and the student. Training with the help of modern computer technologies has a huge motivational potential, allows you to make classes more emotional and informative. However, it should be remembered that communicative tasks in the classroom must first be solved through live communication with the teacher and classmates in a foreign language. The term "multimedia" means: many environments. Such information media are: text, sound, and video. The use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in foreign language lessons is quite relevant for the development of the student's personality and the formation of the following competencies in students: the ability to compare the advantages and disadvantages of various sources of information, choose appropriate search technologies, create and use adequate models and procedures for studying and processing information, etc. Thus, the use of ICT in the process of

teaching foreign languages allows us to speak about positive results in the development of foreign languages and increase the motivation and interest of students.

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